

- *Alligator sinensis* AF511507 **Alligatoridae**
- *Alligator mississippiensis* Y13113 **Alligatoridae**
- *Aptenodytes forsteri* KT159230 **Spheniscidae**
- *Aptenodytes patagonicus* MK801135 **Spheniscidae**
- *Scaphiopus holbrookii* NC 037377 **Scaphiopodidae**
- *Pelodytes cf punctatus* II 2011 NC 020000 **Pelodytidae**
- *Pelobates fuscus* NC 051953 **Pelobatidae**
- *Pelobates cultripes* NC 008144 **Pelobatidae**
- *Megophrys shapingensis* NC 018785 **Megophryidae**
- *Leptobranchella oshanensis* NC 020610 **Megophryidae**
- *Scutigera ningshanensis* NC 031426 **Megophryidae**
- *Leptobranchium leishanense* NC 031411 **Megophryidae**
- *Leptobranchium boringii* NC 024427 **Megophryidae**
- *Oreolalax lichuanensis* NC 030627 **Megophryidae**
- *Oreolalax major* NC 030605 **Megophryidae**
- *Oreolalax omeimontis* NC 049862 **Megophryidae**
- *Oreolalax multipunctatus* NC 037382 **Megophryidae**
- *Leiopelma hochstetteri* NC 027072 **Leiopelmatidae**
- *Leiopelma archeyi* NC 014691 **Leiopelmatidae**
- *Discoglossus galganoi* NC 006690 **Alytidae**
- *Alytes obstetricans pertinax* NC 006688 **Alytidae**
- *Bombina orientalis* NC 006689 **Bombinatoridae**
- *Bombina variegata* NC 009258 **Bombinatoridae**
- *Bombina bombina* NC 042501 **Bombinatoridae**
- *Bombina maxima* NC 011049 **Bombinatoridae**
- *Bombina microdeladigitata* NC 021476 **Bombinatoridae**
- *Bombina lichuanensis* NC 021477 **Bombinatoridae**
- *Bombina fortinuptialis* NC 006402 **Bombinatoridae**
- *Rhinophrynus dorsalis* NC 015620 **Rhinophrynidae**
- *Pseudhymenochirus merlini* NC 015618 **Rhinophrynidae**
- *Hymenochirus boettgeri* NC 015615 **Rhinophrynidae**
- *Pipa carvalhoi* NC 015617 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus tropicalis* NC 006839 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus calcaratus* NC 044865 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus melloittropicalis* NC 044866 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus epitropicalis* NC 044867 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus clivii* NC 044886 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus muelleri* NC 044887 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus fischbergi* NC 044888 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus borealis* NC 018776 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus largeni* NC 044868 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus vestitus* NC 044881 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus lenduensis* NC 044880 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus gilli* NC 044871 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus laevis* NC 001573 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus petersii* NC 044869 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus victorianus* NC 018775 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus poweri* NC 044870 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus parafrazeri* NC 044872 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus pygmaeus* NC 044873 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus allofrazeri* NC 044874 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus wittei* NC 044875 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus itombwensis* NC 044879 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus andrei* NC 044878 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus boumbaensis* NC 044877 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus ruwenzoriensis* NC 044882 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus kobeli* NC 044883 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus amieti* NC 044876 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus longipes* NC 044885 **Pipidae**
- *Xenopus eysoole* NC 044884 **Pipidae**
- *Sooglossus thomasseti* NC 020001 **Sooglossidae**
- *Heleophryne regis* NC 019998 **Heleophrynidae**
- *Lechiodus melanopyga* NC 019999 **Limnodynastidae**
- *Telmatobufo australis* NC 027274 **Calyptocephalellidae**
- *Calyptocephallella gayi* NC 019997 **Calyptocephalellidae**
- *Phyllobates terribilis* NC 037380 **Dendrobatidae**
- *Hyloxalus subpunctatus* NC 037379 **Dendrobatidae**
- *Anomaloglossus baobatrachus* NC 030054 **Dendrobatidae**
- *Anomaloglossus surinamensis* NC 037854 **Dendrobatidae**
- *Anomaloglossus dewynteri* NC 037855 **Dendrobatidae**
- *Anomaloglossus degranvillei* NC 037856 **Dendrobatidae**
- *Anomaloglossus blanci* NC 037857 **Dendrobatidae**
- *Bokermannohyla alvarengai* NC 036493 **Dendrobatidae**
- *Pseudis tocantins* NC 041426 **Dendrobatidae**
- *Hyla chinensis* NC 006403 **Hylidae**
- *Hyla annectans* NC 025309 **Hylidae**
- *Dryophytes versicolor* NC 045917 **Hylidae**
- *Hyla ussuriensis* NC 029410 **Hylidae**
- *Dryophytes japonicus* NC 010232 **Hylidae**
- *Hyla tsinlingensis* NC 026524 **Hylidae**
- *Dryophytes suweonensis* NC 032380 **Hylidae**
- *Telmatobius chusmisensis* NC 030333 **Ceratophryidae**
- *Telmatobius bolivianus* NC 020002 **Ceratophryidae**
- *Melanophryniscus moreirae* NC 037378 **Ceratophryidae**
- *Anaxyrus americanus* NC 047224 **Bufo**
- *Bufo pseudoraddei* NC 046047 **Bufo**
- *Bufo tibundus* NC 050665 **Bufo**
- *Bufo pewzowi* NC 047225 **Bufo**
- *Duttaphrynus melanostictus* NC 005794 **Bufo**
- *Strauchbufo raddei* NC 028424 **Bufo**
- *Bufo tibetanus* NC 020048 **Bufo**
- *Bufo gargarizans* NC 008410 **Bufo**
- *Bufo stejnegeri* NC 027686 **Bufo**
- *Bufo japonicus* NC 009886 **Bufo**
- *Hemisus marmoratus* NC 023380 **Hemisotidae**
- *Breviceps adpersus* NC 023379 **Brevicipitidae**
- *Trichobatrachus robustus* NC 023382 **Arthroleptidae**
- *Hyperolius marmoratus* NC 023381 **Hyperoliidae**
- *Kaloula pulchra* NC 006405 **Microhylidae**
- *Kaloula borealis* NC 020044 **Microhylidae**
- *Kaloula verrucosa* NC 039411 **Microhylidae**
- *Kaloula rugifera* NC 029409 **Microhylidae**
- *Microhyla butleri* NC 030049 **Microhylidae**
- *Microhyla taraiensis* NC 039176 **Microhylidae**
- *Microhyla pulchra* NC 024547 **Microhylidae**
- *Microhyla heymonsi* NC 006406 **Microhylidae**
- *Microhyla ornata* NC 009422 **Microhylidae**
- *Microhyla fissipes* NC 045110 **Microhylidae**
- *Microhyla okinavensis* NC 010233 **Microhylidae**
- *Microhyla mixtura* NC 038130 **Microhylidae**
- *Cornufer vitianus* NC 027671 **Ceratobatrachidae**
- *Pyxicephalus adpersus* NC 044480 **Pyxicephalidae**
- *Mantella madagascariensis* NC 007888 **Mantellidae**
- *Mantella baroni* NC 039758 **Mantellidae**
- *Buergeria buergeri* NC 008975 **Rhacophoridae**
- *Polypedates mutus* MN869009 **Rhacophoridae**
- *Polypedates braueri* NC 042797 **Rhacophoridae**
- *Polypedates megacephalus* NC 043955 **Rhacophoridae**
- *Polypedates impresus* MN869008 **Rhacophoridae**
- *Zhangixalus dennysi* NC 027452 **Rhacophoridae**
- *Zhangixalus omeimontis* NC 046387 **Rhacophoridae**
- *Zhangixalus schlegelii* NC 007178 **Rhacophoridae**
- *Zhangixalus arboreus* LC565708 **Rhacophoridae**
- *Occidozyga martensii* NC 014685 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Euphyctis hexadactylus* NC 014584 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus* NC 014581 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Hoplobatrachus rugulosus* NC 019615 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Fejervarya cancrivora* NC 012647 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Fejervarya multistriata* NC 029754 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Fejervarya limnocharis* NC 005055 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Limnonectes fujianensis* NC 007440 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Quasipaa yei* NC 024843 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Quasipaa spinosa* NC 013270 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Quasipaa boulengeri* NC 021937 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Nanorana taihangnica* NC 024272 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Nanorana parkeri* NC 026789 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Nanorana ventripunctata* NC 039094 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Nanorana pleskei* NC 016119 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Amolops wuyiensis* NC 025591 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Amolops ricketti* NC 023949 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Amolops granulatus* NC 044901 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Amolops mantzorum* NC 024180 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Amolops lotoensis* NC 029250 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax chosienicus* NC 016059 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax plancyi* NC 009264 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax nigromaculatus* NC 002805 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax shqipericus* NC 026896 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax epeiroticus* NC 026894 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax cretensis* NC 025575 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax bedriagae* NC 029200 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax kurtmuelleri* NC 026895 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax cypriensis* NC 026893 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax cf bedriagae* GM178 NC 029201 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax cf bedriagae* MPFC1082 NC 029197 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax cf bedriagae* AFL1 NC 029196 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax cf terentievi* MPFC1736 NC 029199 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Pelophylax cf terentievi* GM87 239 NC 029198 **Dicoglossidae**
- *Glandirana emeljanovi* NC 030211 **Ranidae**
- *Babina subaspera* NC 022871 **Ranidae**
- *Babina holsti* NC 022870 **Ranidae**
- *Nidirana okinavana* NC 022872 **Ranidae**
- *Sylvirana guentheri* NC 024748 **Ranidae**
- *Babina adenopleura* NC 018771 **Ranidae**
- *Odorrana ishikawae* NC 015305 **Ranidae**
- *Odorrana wuchuanensis* NC 034983 **Ranidae**
- *Odorrana margaretae* NC 024603 **Ranidae**
- *Odorrana schmackeri* NC 027827 **Ranidae**
- *Odorrana hainanensis* NC 034984 **Ranidae**
- *Odorrana tormota* NC 009423 **Ranidae**
- *Odorrana livida* NC 043768 **Ranidae**
- *Odorrana graminea* NC 050888 **Ranidae**
- *Lithobates sylvaticus* NC 027236 **Ranidae**
- *Lithobates okaloosae* NC 028283 **Ranidae**
- *Lithobates catesbeianus* NC 022696 **Ranidae**
- *Rana draytonii* NC 028296 **Ranidae**
- *Rana temporaria* NC 042226 **Ranidae**
- *Rana kunyensis* NC 024548 **Ranidae**
- *Rana amurensis* NC 030042 **Ranidae**
- *Rana omeimontis* NC 035805 **Ranidae**
- *Rana chaochiaoensis* NC 035803 **Ranidae**
- *Rana dybowskii* NC 023528 **Ranidae**
- *Rana huanrensis* NC 028521 **Ranidae**
- *Rana kukunoris* NC 035804 **Ranidae**
- *Rana cf chensinensis* QYCRCC C NC 023529 **Ranidae**